

Educational Law Panacea For Enhancing Tertiary Education Quality in Nigeria

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Abstract: *The paper explores the importance of educational laws in the realization of tertiary education quality in Nigeria. Depending on secondary data which were collected from both online and print resources the paper concludes that full implementation of educational laws in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria will lead to improvement in the system and attainment of quality education in the tertiary institutions. Based, on the findings, the paper recommends that government and tertiary education stakeholders should ensure policies and laws on tertiary education are fully implemented in all tertiary institutions. The National Universities Commission [NUC], National Commission for Colleges of Education [NCCE] and the National Board for Technical Education [NBTE] should ensure effective supervision of all tertiary institutions to ensure adherence to the various laws and policies of tertiary institutions.*

Keywords: *Education, Educational Laws, Tertiary Education.*

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Date of Submission: 02 Tertiary education refers to all *formal* post-secondary education, including public and private universities, colleges, technical training institutes, and vocational schools. Tertiary education is instrumental in fostering growth, reducing poverty, and boosting shared prosperity. A highly skilled workforce, with lifelong access to a solid post-secondary education, is a prerequisite for innovation and growth: well-educated people are more employable and productive, earn higher wages, and cope with economic shocks better (World-bank, 2024). Tertiary education is defined by National policy on Education (2013) as the education given after Post Basic Education in institutions such as Universities and Inter-University Centres such as the Nigeria French Language Village, Nigeria Arabic Language Village, National Institute of Nigerian Languages, institutions such as Innovation Enterprise Institutions (IEIs), and Colleges of Education, Monotechnics, Polytechnics, and other specialized institutions such as Colleges of Agriculture, Schools of Health and Technology and the National Teachers' Institutes (NTI). Tertiary education can be defined as the planned and organized system of learning designed for the total development

of individuals and the total transformation of the society through the utilization of teaching, research and provision of community service (Ogunode, Edinoh & Okolie 2023).

Also, tertiary education or higher education according to Alamo (2018) covers a wider range of higher learning institutions including the university. These higher learning institutions could be organized in different ways, commonly within a university and in a separate institution as university and other tertiary learning institutions. Tertiary education fosters individual development and growth as well as impacts positively on the society at large (Schrader-King, 2024). From the above, tertiary education can be seen in this paper as a post-secondary education that is teaching, research and community service inclined. Tertiary education is a specialized education in a specific field that is taken up after finishing secondary school that focus on teaching, research and provision of community services. Tertiary education is non-compulsory education system and that is provided in higher institutions of learning such as college, polytechnic or university with aims of manpower development and training.

The goals of tertiary education according to the FGN National Policy on Education (2013), shall be to: contribute to national development through high level manpower training; provide accessible and affordable quality learning opportunities in formal and informal education in response to the needs and interests of all Nigerians; provide high quality career counseling and lifelong learning programmes that prepare students with the knowledge and skills for selfreliance and the world of work; reduce skill shortages through the production of skilled manpower relevant to the needs of the labour market; promote and encourage scholarship, entrepreneurship and community service; forge and cement national unity; and promote national and international understanding and interaction.

The attainment of tertiary education goals depends to the availability of adequate human, materials resources and enabling laws for effective operation. Laws are also decisions and provisions for the establishment and protection of fundamental human rights. They intend to regulate relationship between individuals, groups, organizations, institutions etc. Igwe (2003) observed that education laws helps to ensure justice, peace, maintain order, co—existence and interaction among members despite their divergent interests and aspirations. The enactment and promulgation of educational laws for the administration and management of education especially tertiary education in Nigeria is key to the development of education. It is important to discuss the important of educational laws in enhancing quality education in Tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Literature Review

Education is an organized process of teaching and learning made up of instruction designed to change the behavior of the learner for transformation of the society and nation. Education is a planned system involving teaching and learning process for the transformation of the individual and the nation (Ogunode, Kureh, & Kasimu, 2024). Education is the most powerful instrument for inculcating into citizens of any country good attributes and values for national building. Through education a child's attitude and character is sharpened with the relevant skills, knowledge and competences needed to contribute to social, economic and political development of the society. It is a fundamental human right as everybody has the right to be educated. Education is one of the main drivers of development, be it human, economic or political (Asiyai, 2020). Education is one of the largest human organisation which services affect everyone in the society. It is also perceived as the panacea to the problems of ignorance, poverty and disease. Consequently, everybody in the society is concerned with the question of how this large human organization is managed, especially as there appears to be a strong and positive linkage between education and national development (Kadir, 2018). The role of education in building members of the society to enable them fit into the society and solve its problems underscores its importance. To maximize these benefits, the law has created

certain principles to regulate the education sector and this manifest in the form of laws, policies and cases collectively referred to as education law (Emmanuel, 2024). From the above, education can be seen a process that is made up of teaching and learning that is meant to transform the individual and make them useful to the society. Education is an instrument for behavior modification and national development. Education is process which involves practical teaching and learning in educational institutions using curriculum, instructional resources and professional teachers as facilitator.

Educational laws are official laws formulated to aid effective administration and management of education in a country or state. Educational laws are sets of laws, rules and policies designed and formulated passed into laws to be used for the management of education in a country (Ogunode, Nwisagbo, & Telema, 2025). Education laws are simply those laws that have been enacted specifically for the organization and administration and control of the education system. He explained that education laws were promulgated as ordinances during the colonial era, and during the military regime, the education laws were issued as decrees or edicts by the federal government (Nwagu 2003). Education law can be defined according to Emmanuel, (2024) as a body of rules, regulations, policies and cases that guide the education sector in order to make it quality, inclusive and accessible. Education laws regulate the activities of all stakeholders in the sector including, but not limited to, learners, teachers, parents, school support workers like health workers, school administrators, private investors, government and other stakeholders. For example, the Teacher Registration Council of Nigeria Act regulates the teaching profession while the various statues and laws setting up the various universities regulate their operations. Peretomode in Igwe (2010) defines “education law as those areas of jurisprudence which focuses on educational activities – the operation of public and private elementary, secondary and post-secondary institutions of learning”.

Education laws are simply those laws that have been enacted specifically for the organisation, administration and control of the education system. Although those who operate in the education enterprise are citizens governed by the laws of the land, criminal or civil as the case may be, they are also expected to comply with laws designed exclusively to regulate what we can do or not do in the process of teaching, learning and management. The education laws are necessary because educational establishment or institution is a social organisation with many individuals and groups as stakeholders. There are many complex aims and objectives to achieve and numerous diverse interests, aspirations and expectations to satisfy. The need to regulate social interaction and behaviour appears obvious or imperative (NOUN 2012). Education law includes ‘dos’ and ‘don’ts’ and implications of such acts in the operations of the school system (Maduagwu 2006),

Educational law refers to the body of laws and regulations that govern the field of education. It encompasses a wide range of legal issues related to educational institutions, students, teachers, administrators, and the educational system as a whole. Educational law addresses matters such as student rights, teacher responsibilities, curriculum development, school funding, discrimination, and other legal aspects associated with the educational sector (Dibra 2021). Education law can be regarded as an area of jurisprudence, which covers a wide range of legal subject matters relating to the principles and practices of establishment and operation of public and private education institutions (Agabi and Ukala in Agabi, et al., 2005). From the above education laws is a set of rule and regulation formulated and designed for education management for the purpose of ensuring standard. Education law is a legal instrument designed for administering and regulating education in a country. Education law refer to an official policy designed for regulating and managing education with the aims of maintaining education standard. Educational law is a policy formulated by ministry of education and some of its agencies that is back by decree to be used for the management of education with the purpose of ensuring quality in the system and maintaining standard in all educational institutions.

The importance of education law includes; to improve quality of education; to ensure standard in education; to ensure accountability in education; to ensure effective use of education resources; to protect citizen' rights to education; to provide direction for clear coordination of education at every level of government; to define the education right of citizens; and to provide legal document to regulate education.

Method

This paper is a review paper. It employed systematic literature review-based method. Previous literature from both online publications and print sources were review. Content analysis was used to select secondary information on this topic. The method adopted followed a systematic review processes based narrative design. The first process began by sourcing materials online and in print materials identified, downloaded and collected. The second step involves selection and organization of literatures that have direct link to the topic. The previous findings are critically analyzed and presented in different themes on the importance of educational laws in enhancing quality education in tertiary institutions.

Data Analysis

Full Implementation of Educational Law Panacea for Enhancing Tertiary Education in Nigeria

NOUN (2012) and Ogunode and Adeola (2023) observed that full application of educational laws in the Nigeria's tertiary institutions has the capacity to improve the standard of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Dibra, (2021) submitted the implementation of the various policies and laws of tertiary institution can help solve numerous problems facing the higher institutions in Nigeria.

Ken, (2018) and Musa (2022) maintained that the development of tertiary education depends on the extent to which the various policies and laws are implemented. He went further to observe that implementation of financial laws will help to strengthen the system and reduce corruption in the system. Agabi, and Ukala, (2005) and Igwe, (2010) remarked that full implementation of education laws in Nigeria will help to improve the quality of education and help to instill accountability and transparency. Uche, (2016) noted that educational laws are designed to enhance effective management and delivery of quality in the system.

Omoniyi (2013) and Jacob (2014) opined that the full implementation of the tertiary education policies will enhance development and realization of tertiary education goals. Johnson (2016) ascertained that the education laws have the capacity to improve the quality of teaching and research in the higher institutions. Ogunode, & Adeola, (2023) and Okebukola (2018) concluded that the implementation of students-teacher ratio policies, minimum teachers' qualification policies and admission policies will help to improve quality in the system of tertiary institutions across the country. Uche (2016) and Ogunode, et al (2025) submitted that educational laws will help strengthen quality assurance, graduate output and manpower development.

Findings

The paper discovered that educational laws is vital to the realization of quality tertiary education in Nigeria. The paper concludes that full implementation of educational laws in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria will lead to improvement in the system and attainment of quality education in the tertiary institutions.

Conclusion and Recommendations

The paper explores the importance of educational laws in the realization of quality tertiary education in Nigeria. The paper concludes that full implementation of educational laws in the

tertiary institutions in Nigeria will lead to improvement in the system and attainment of quality education in the tertiary institutions.

Based, on the findings, the paper recommends that government and tertiary education stakeholders should ensure policies and laws on tertiary education are fully implemented in all tertiary institutions. The National Universities Commission [NUC], National Commission for Colleges of Education [NCCE] and the National Board for Technical Education [NBTE] should ensure effective supervision of all tertiary institutions to ensure adherence to the various laws and policies of tertiary institutions.

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